

WP3 Methodology Note

Expert interview study with Swiss and Bulgarian retailers on the listing of NGT (CRISPR-edited) products

Project: Addressing the Genetically Modified Agricultural Products Conundrum — A Holistic Approach
SciEx IZSF-0_235780 (Swiss National Science Foundation) • Sofia University «St. Kliment Ohridski»
and Agroscope • Version 1, 01.07.2026

1. Purpose and design

The study is a semi-structured expert (key-informant) interview study of senior decision-makers in **retail trade** organisations in Switzerland and Bulgaria. The target interviewee is the person with authority over, or substantial influence on, strategic listing decisions for new, regulatorily sensitive product categories: members of the executive board (Geschäftsleitung), directors of buying or category management, and senior category managers responsible for fresh produce, fruit and vegetables, dairy or meat. The objective is to identify who decides on the listing of NGT (CRISPR-edited) products, under which criteria, and how those criteria differ across structurally distinct types of trading organisations.

2. Sampling

Sampling is purposive with criterion-based selection, stratified along three dimensions, with snowball expansion. The sampling frame is built from publicly verifiable sources and from targeted referrals. The full Switzerland and Bulgaria sampling matrices, sorted by priority, are set out in the companion Recruitment Protocol. Stratification follows: **segment; ownership structure and region and language**. This ensures the sample is not dominated by a single perspective and that the Switzerland–Bulgaria comparison is balanced across ownership types. Working languages are German, English and Bulgarian; French is a contingent language for Romandie respondents subject to feasibility.

Inclusion criteria: a strategic role in category management, buying or executive leadership of a retail organisation operating in Switzerland or Bulgaria; at least two years of relevant experience; capacity to speak to decisions on new regulatorily sensitive product categories; and written informed consent. **Exclusion criteria:** persons in purely operational roles (store managers without category responsibility); persons in Public Affairs or Communications roles, whose function is to articulate the organisation's external voice rather than the internal logic of decisions; and persons with whom a direct commercial contract exists in the project, to avoid conflicts of interest.

Target sample size: per country, a minimum of 10 interviews and a target of 12 to 14, comparable across the two samples for parallel analysis. A buffer of two additional interviewees allows adaptation in case of refusal or non-relevant responses.

3. Saturation criterion

The criterion distinguishes code saturation (no substantively new first-level codes emerge) from meaning saturation (full elaboration of identified themes). In a quasi-monopolistic market with a small population of relevant decision-makers, theoretical saturation is reached substantially earlier than in population-based studies; the expert-interview literature identifies 10 to 12 interviews as sufficient to cover the majority of the variation expert population as in our case. Operationally, saturation is claimed only when two consecutive interviews within a country arm yield no new first-level codes and no substantive new dimensions of existing codes. If saturation is not demonstrated by the twelfth interview, recruitment continues up to the fourteenth prior to closure.

4. Analytic strategy

The analytic strategy is framework analysis (deductive thematic layers to which inductive aspects are added as a parallel layer). Coding proceeds in five stages: familiarisation with full transcripts; construction of an initial coding framework deductively from the propositions; indexing of transcripts against the framework; inductive emergence of additional themes; and charting, mapping and interpretation. An independent second coder codes a random subset of the transcripts; inter-rater agreement is assessed and discrepancies resolved through discussion. A cluster analysis may then be performed to derive a typology of retailer responses. The comparative analysis runs between countries (Switzerland versus Bulgaria) and within ownership types where the design permits direct pairing (for example, Lidl Switzerland with Lidl Bulgaria).

5. Ethics and data protection

Informed consent is obtained in writing prior to each interview using the deposited Consent Form template (German/English and Bulgarian). The expected interview duration is approximately 60 minutes. Recording is conducted only with explicit consent; where it is declined, contemporaneous notes are taken instead. Anonymisation operates at two levels: personal anonymisation is the default, and organisational anonymisation is offered as an option, with de-anonymisation at organisational level only against the explicit written consent of the participant. Commercially sensitive details (specific pricing data, supplier contracts, planned non-public listings) are excluded from the interview guide.

Pseudonymisation occurs at transcription. Storage is on the secured Agroscope servers, in line with the Data Management Plan (DMP) submitted to the Swiss National Science Foundation under project IZSF-0_235780, with retention of at least ten years after project completion. Data processing complies with the revised Swiss Federal Act on Data Protection (revFADP / nDSG, in force since 01.09.2023) for Swiss-side processing, and with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation (EU) 2016/679) and the Bulgarian Personal Data Protection Act (ЗЗЛД) for the Bulgarian arm. The hosting institution and data controller is Agroscope (Federal Research Institute for Agriculture). The procedural instruments of the study contain no personal data within the meaning of GDPR Art. 4(1) or the Bulgarian Personal Data Protection Act, and are pre-registered on a repository aligned with the FAIR principles (such as Zenodo) under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) licence prior to the first interview. Any subsequent deposit of fieldwork-derived artefacts is conditional on the approval of Agroscope as data controller under the DMP; the Recruitment Tracker, which contains personal data, is never published.

Ethics approval has been obtained from two independent Bulgarian ethics committees, whose remit covers both country arms of the project: (i) the Ethics Committee of Sofia University «St. Kliment Ohridski» (ref. № 93-K-72/17.04.2026; chair Prof. Dr Romyana Marinova-Hristidi); and (ii) the Ethics Committee of the Bulgarian Sociological Association (session of 15.05.2026; chair Prof. Dr Tatyana Kotseva).